

Random Matrices, Gaussian Distributions and Level Crossing Avoidance Part II

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In Part I, we tried to examine the result $P(s) = .5s \exp(-ss/4)$, where $P(s)$ is the probability for the spacing s between two Hamiltonian eigenvalues in a random matrix. In (1), it is noted that $P(x=0)=0$, i.e. level crossing is avoided, even in a Hermitian random matrix (i.e. probability distributed matrix element picture). We argued that solutions of the Schrodinger equation (or other eigenvalue differential equations) lead to discrete energy eigenvalues and orthogonal eigenfunctions. We suggested that this orthogonality pushes the eigenfunctions and eigenvalues apart, so to speak, so that they do not become arbitrarily close. In other words, there is an inherent constraint associated with eigenvalues in the linear algebra of Hermitian matrices which is separate from the probability distribution one may apply to the elements.

In this note, we examine again the random matrix calculation which leads to $P(s) = .5s \exp(-ss/4)$. We note that even though one does not have an exact Hamiltonian, the 2x2 matrix model leading to the $P(s)$ result is based on finding eigenvalues. In general, these are distinct. We suggested that a constant probability distribution for eigenvalues allows for them to be arbitrarily close which contradicts the idea of orthogonal eigenvectors and eigenvalues. As a result, an additional constraint is needed. We revisit this idea here so show how the separation of eigenvalues leads to such a specific constraint if $s=0$. Thus, it seems that it is the nature of a Hermitian matrix trying to keep its eigenvalues distinct which leads to the $P(s=0)=0$ result. We consider, as in (1), a calculation using only distribution probabilities of energy levels which leads to a result which does not exhibit $P(s)=0$, as this physical/mathematical condition is not enforced anywhere in the calculation like is in the case of a Hermitian matrix.

Schrodinger Equation

As noted in Part I, the Schrodinger, Klein-Gordon, Dirac equations etc. represent eigenvalue differential equations which mathematically lead to discrete energy eigenvalues and orthogonal eigenfunctions. These eigenfunctions are linked to spatial density and so are physical. Thus, physically, different resonance (bound states) try to separate themselves spatially as well as in terms of energy values. As argued in Part I, this physical feature must be retained if one tries to approximate the exact solution of energy eigenvalues for a given Hamiltonian H with some kind of statistical distribution approach. The question then seems to be: How does one enforce the orthogonality of eigenfunctions which tends to force distinct eigenvalues? Simply choosing a probability distribution for a eigenvalue values does not seem to be sufficient. A constraint must somehow be introduced.

Random Matrix

In (1), a 2x2 Hermitian random matrix (i.e. x_1, x_3 on the first row and x_3, x_2 on the second, with x_i being distributed according to a probability distribution) is considered. We first note that a probability distribution which is independent for each x_i imposes no restrictions on two x_i values being the same. The physical separation of energy eigenvalues must enter in a different way. We suggest that it enters through the nature of the eigenvalues .

The 2x2 matrix, described above, has eigenvalues which satisfy:

$$\det (M - bI) = 0 \text{ where } M \text{ is the matrix, } b \text{ the eigenvalue, and } I, \text{ the identity matrix. ((1))}$$

$$\text{or } 2b = x_1 + x_2 \pm \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)(x_1 - x_2) + 4x_3x_3} \quad ((2))$$

The Hermitian matrix is guaranteed to have distinct, real eigenvalues. The eigenvectors are

orthogonal. Thus, linear algebra seems to ensure that eigenvalues are pushed apart. The spacing of the two eigenvalues is:

$$s = \sqrt{(x_1-x_2)(x_1-x_2) + 4x_3x_3} \quad ((3))$$

One may see that in order to have $s=0$, $x_1=x_2$ and $x_3=0$. This leads to a diagonal Hamiltonian matrix, but with two identical energy eigenvalues which contradicts the physical/mathematical nature of the Hamiltonian which deals with different energy resonances. Thus, the $s=0$ case, is pathological in the sense that it forces the two energy eigenvalues to be the same. More importantly, however, it forces x_3 to take a specific value, namely 0, and the probability for an exact number (not a small range) seems to be 0. Even though any $x_1-x_2=0$ values are acceptable, only $x_3=0$ is for $s=0$ and this leads to a zero probability. It seems to be the nature of a Hermitian matrix, even a random one, trying to separate its eigenvalues (and eigenfunctions) which leads to the $P(s=0)=0$ result.

Only in the unusual case of the two eigenvalues being identical does one have $s=0$, which is a rare case as it occurs for $x_3=0$, a discrete value and not a probability range.

We note here that the independent distribution used to describe the probability distribution of x_i is not sufficient for ensuring energy level crossing avoidance. It is the nature of the distinct matrix elements which seems to ensure this. As argued in Part I, if one wishes to mimic the behaviour of energy levels for a physical Hamiltonian, one cannot arbitrarily eliminate important information such as the orthogonality of eigenfunctions and the tendency for discrete energy eigenvalues.

In (1), a second calculation is presented which does not ensure this constraint, i.e. only uses probability distributions for the energy levels. This leads to a result for which $P(x=0) \neq 0$.

No Distinct Eigenvalue Constraint

We argued above that an exact Hamiltonian solution (Schrodinger equation etc) or a 2×2 matrix approach are both based on discrete eigenvalues. Even if one considers a random Hermitian matrix, the eigenvalue behaviour enforces distinct eigenvalues which leads to $P(s=0) = 0$.

What happens if one does not have such a constraint on energy eigenvalues? In other words, what if one only considers probability distributions for n energy eigenvalues which are considered to be independent? Such a calculation is presented in (1) and we examine it here.

Consider $p(x)$ to be the probability of for an energy level to be at x and $F(x)$ to be the cumulative probability for it to be between minus infinite and x . Then, if one has n energy levels, one is at x , the other at $x+s$, and the $n-2$ remaining points are either less than x or greater than $x+s$. The energy levels are considered to be independent so for each $n-2$ level, the probability is: $(F(x) + 1-F(x+s))$. Given that there are $n-2$ levels, one multiplies this factor $n-2$ times. Thus:

$$P(s) = C \int dx \ p(x) p(x+s) (F(x) + 1-F(x+s))^{n-2} \quad ((4))$$

with $p(x) = d/dx F(x)$.

(1) computes ((4)) in the n approaches infinite limit and finds the result proportional to:

$$\exp(-s) \text{ where } s \text{ is the spacing between two energy eigenvalues} \quad ((5))$$

One sees immediately that $\exp(-0)=1$, i.e. there is a finite probability to have energy levels touching. This seems to follow from the fact that the probability distributions for each level do not impose any constraint which keeps levels apart and there is no built-in discrete energy eigenvalue constraint from a Hermitian matrix. We suggest that one should treat ((5)) with caution because it eliminates information, i.e. a constraint of discreted energy eigenvalues, present in an original exact Schrodinger equation solution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that calculations of $P(s)$, the probability for a spacing of s between energy eigenvalues, depends on more than independent probability distributions for energy eigenvalues, because an exact solution of the Schrodinger equation and even a solution of eigenvalues of a 2×2 Hermitian matrix contain an inherent constraint of distinct eigenvalues. This inherent constraint leads to an avoidance of energy level touching (crossing) or $P(s=0)=0$. In particular, a calculation using the exact energy eigenvalue form or a matrix $\begin{pmatrix} x_1 & x_3 \\ x_3 & x_2 \end{pmatrix}$ on the first row, x_3, x_2 on the second) leads to $P(s) = .5s \exp(-ss/4)$, i.e. Wigner's result. This result ensues, we argue, because there is only one way to have $s=0$ and that is to have $x_3=0$, which being a discrete value has a probability tending to 0. The fact that one uses probability distributions to describe the values of x_1, x_2, x_3 does not ensure such a constraint. In fact, it seems to point to the opposite conclusion because independent probabilities for energy eigenvalues suggests that they may be arbitrarily close to each other. This idea seems to be specifically born out in a calculation presented in (1), namely using n energy eigenvalues with one at x , another $x+s$ and the rest outside the region $(x, x+s)$. This leads to $P(s) = C \exp(-s)$ which is finite for $s=0$ as nowhere does one impose any constraint forcing energy eigenvalues to be discrete, i.e. different.

References

1. Livan, G. And Novaes, M. And Vivo, P. Introduction to Random Matrices Theory and Practices 2017 [1712.07903.pdf \(arxiv.org\)](#)